

Performance of the Dynamic Range Limited Optical OFDM Schemes with Error Correction Coding

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ABSTRACT

Optical wireless communication is a potent technology for future indoor and outdoor communication. Currently unipolar OFDM schemes have been introduced to compensate for the limitation like inter symbol interference and multipath fading. This work presents the error correction coding for unipolar OFDM schemes to improve the BER performance. In particular, hamming code was used to improve the BER vs LED dynamic range performance. Finally results, from simulation, reveals the improvement of the coded optical OFDM schemes with un-coded optical OFDM schemes.

I INTRODUCTION

Power Line Radio Frequency (RF) is a type of electromagnetic radiation used for radio communication to transmit data having frequency range 3KHZ to 300GHZ, however RF is regulated with limited range of bandwidth while infrared (IR) is non-regulated with unlimited bandwidth. Hence IR is preferring rather than RF for short range communication. As IR is near to visible light so they both have almost common features and advantage [1]. However, IR have a primary drawback relates to eye safety and skin issues, to avoid this Researchers trend their

attention toward visible light communication (VLC). Hence VLC is being safe and prefer over IR to transmit information by the use of visible light.

VLC is a light dependent wireless communication network that use light as a carrier and air as an unguided propagation media. In VLC the transmitter consists of laser diode (LD) or light emitting diode (LED), Whereas the receiver of VLC is photo diode (PD) and transimpedance amplifier (TIA). Signals transmit through intensity modulation and recover at Direct deduction, So the system is called as intensity modulation direct detection. When signals pass through

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channel and reach at receiver, as there are Photo Detectors that convert the light again into electrical signals [2].

VLC is a very low power consumption system. It can allow much high data rate due to having very high bandwidth than other Communication methods.

VLC is much secure as compare to others, because the signals transmit through visible light that can't pass through any solid objects. i.e. walls etc. It is independent of line of sight.

Due to visibility of light, it can transmit data for long distances. Different techniques use for high-speed optical wireless communication. Initially if we increase speed a problem comes that is called as inter symbol interference (ISI). The main problem in VLC is ISI. To overcome this at high frequency we have a technique that is called as orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM). OFDM is a Modulation technique that divides the data into multiple subcarriers each carrying a small portion of data stream [3]. As OFDM is a bipolar technique but here in optical intensity no concept of bipolar i.e. negative light is meaning less so we have to use unipolar OFDM [4]. Hence different unipolar OFDM schemes are reported which are characterize as DC biased optical OFDM (DCO OFDM), asymmetrically clipped optical OFDM (ACO OFDM), Flip OFDM etc. These schemes are investigated for power efficiency, energy efficiency, Peak to average power ratio (PAPR) and bite error rate (BER). These schemes are normally implemented without error correction and their performances are still limited. So in order to enhance their performance, error correction code is added to the data to detect and correct errors that may occur during transition. Optical unipolar OFDM is characterized by their BER performance vs dynamic. The reported BER schemes are used without error-correction. Hence the BER vs Dynamic range (DR) performance with error correction coding requires an investigation.

II Coded Unipolar OFDM System design

System design with error correction code for DCO optical OFDM is depicting in figure 1. where the basic error correction code (hamming code) is used to enhance the reliability of data transmission by enabling single bit error correction. 1st bits are interring through the hamming code as subcarriers to the input of a transmitter for a DCO OFDM schemes then they are mapped in Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM) symbols with the help of QAM mapper by converting the given data into groups.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the flow chart

As the input data contains complex number so in order to make it real and hermitian symmetry is arranged in the input of the IFFT in such a way that it gives real instead of complex then this obtained real signal is applied to a Parallel to serial converter (P/S) which converts the data from parallel to serial, and to prevent the ISI a cyclic prefix (CP) is applied to the OFDM signal and clipping is used for the limited range then the data is applied through a digital to analog converter (DAC) wherein it is converted from digital signal to analog so that it can transmit through a physical channel and finally a DC biased is added to make the signal positive and unipolar, hence the signal is passed through the channel [5]. On the other hand at the receiver an analog to digital converter (A/D) is used to converts the signal from analog to digital and a cyclic prefix is removed then a serial to parallel (S/P) converter is applied to convert the data from serial to parallel for the input of FFT and an equalizer is used to regain the channel impairments and a decoding is used to decode the data and a P/S converter is applied to bring the data in original form hence data out and bite error rate (BER) is used to bits error rate.

In this paper the Hamming code is used to encode the 40 data bits. The 40 data bits are arranged in 6 groups by using the two types of Hamming code that are the (7,4) bits and (12,8) bits code according to these data bits the 22 parity bits are added in the 40 data bits to encode the 62-bit code word.

Transmitter format

In (7,4) hamming code the 4 data bits and 3 parity bits are used to make the 7-bit code word as shown in table 1.

Table 1: (7,4) Hamming code,

D4	D3	D2	P3	D1	P2	P1
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Similarly, the 8 data bit and 4 parity bits are used to make the total of 12 bits in (12,8) hamming code as shown in table 2.

Table 2: (12,8) Hamming code

D8	D7	D6	D5	P4	D4	D3	D2	P3	D1	P2	P1
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Receiver format

In this arrangement the (7,4) Hamming code is used two times and (12,8) Hamming code is used 4 times to encode the total of 62 bits. In 1st kind of coding the 8 data bits are divided in to 2 groups of 4 bits and by adding 3 parity bits in each group so each group make the code word length of 8 bits.

Table 3: (7,4) Hamming code

D4	D3	D2	P3	D1	P2	P1
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Table 4: (12,8) Hamming code

D8	D7	D6	D5	P4	D4	D3	D2	P3	D1	P2	P1
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Similarly, in the other type the 32 data bits are encode into 4 groups of 8 bit each and by adding 4 parity bits in each group according to the given data bits. So, they make the total of 12 bits. By combining these all bits, the 62 bits are formed that are used to encode the data before transmission.

IV Results

The channel gain is different for different sub carrier’s frequencies; it is not similar for different frequencies. However, the channel gain is similar for both cases, coded as well as un-coded optical OFDM schemes as shown in figure2.

Figure 2: Channel gain at 10Mb/s

The BER vs DR performance for un coded optical OFDM is shown in figure 3 where the curve starts from 0.4 and decreases gradually till of the order of 10⁻³.

Figure 3: BER vs Dynamic range performance for 10Mb/s

BER vs DR performance of coded optical OFDM scheme is shown in figure 4 where the analytical and simulation is matched. The BER values ranges from 10^{-0.4} to 10⁻⁴

Figure 4: BER vs Dynamic range performance for coded optical OFDM scheme for 10Mb/s

The BER vs DR performance for coded and un-coded optical OFDM is shown in figure 5, where the blue curve shows the un-coded while the red curve shows the response of coded optical OFDM.

Figure 5: Comparison of BER Vs DR performance of coded and un-coded optical OFDM

The un-coded curve is initially at 0.4 while the coded curve starts from 0.6. Where we can see that the correction shows

a good impact for low signal power because at low intensity the probability of error occurs so here the error correction is more helpful.

V Conclusion

Unipolar OFDM schemes are introduced to improve BER. The channel gain is not same for all carriers depending upon their frequencies. The Analytical and simulation performance for BER vs DR for un coded optical OFDM almost match similarly in coded optical OFDM the simulation performance is at -4.

There is a difference of 0.2 between coded and un-coded performance for BER vs DR performance so the coded performance shows good result as compare to un-coded.

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